

resistant varieties as possible replacements for locally grown Mangala

(see table). The most promising varieties were IET7633 and IET7614, both of

Rasi Finegora, and IET7261 from Rasi Mettasamma. *ℳ*

BG367-4, a promising short-duration rice

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BG3674 (BG280-12/PTB 33) is a promising short-duration rice received through the International Rice Testing

Program. It was evaluated at PES in the 1980 International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON), and performed well in 1980-84 in Jun-Sep.

BG367-4 yielded 9.5 t ha in 1983, with average yields of 6.5 t ha over 4 yr. It yielded 25% more than TKM9 and 35% more than ADT36 (see table). Duration ranged from 109 to 115 d, averaging 112 d.

BG3674 has semidwarf (91 cm)

stature, long slender grains, and white rice. The 1,000-grain weight is 23.4 g.

Yield potential is high because of high panicle weight (1.33 g).

The variety has been nominated for the 1985-86 Rice Coordinated Yield Trial-2 (100-120 d) at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University experiment stations and is being used as a donor in the PES hybridization program. *ℳ*

Performance of BG367-4 at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						Flowering time (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	1000-grain wt (g)	Panicle wt (g)
	IRON 1980	Yield trial 1981	Yield trial 1982	IRYN (VE) 1983	Yield trial 1984	IRYN (VE) 1984					
BG3674	6.9	5.5	5.1	9.5	6.1	6.1	82	91	8.3	23.4	1.33
ADT36	5.1	4.4	5.2	—	4.1	5.4	84	84	8.9	24.2	1.16
TKM9	—	5.0	5.3	6.6	4.3	4.6	82	82	8.2	24.5	1.27
m + σ	6.9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)	—	1.1	0.5	1.4	0.1	1.3	—	—	—	—	—

Evaluation of six rice genotypes in relation to field hydrology

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We evaluated the effect of drought on yield of six rices with different durations in 1983 wet and 1984 semiwet seasons.

In both seasons, the rices were planted on 7 Sep and grown with similar agronomic practices. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time were recorded (Fig. 1). Drought was longer and more severe in semiwet season. Evaporation exceeded precipitation 11 wk after seeding in semiwet season and after 16 wk in wet season. In semiwet season, groundwater level was below 80 cm 12 wk after seeding.

Short-duration MW 10 performed best in semiwet season, yielding 2.5 t/ha. Late-maturing Mahsuri yielded lowest, 0.3 t/ha. Poorva, IR36, Usha, and Safri 17 produced intermediate yields. Safri 17

Water table depth (cm)

Weekly evaporation and rainfall (mm)

1. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time of 6 genotypes. Kaipur, India